

Important Issues of Using Video Materials in Esp Classes

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Abstract: This article explains the importance of video materials in ESP classes and outlines the classification of them. Authentic video materials create favorable conditions for the students to master new information, the speech behavior of native speakers, and help them to be acquainted with the life of the people and culture as well.

Key points: video materials, teaching English, native speakers, visual representations, speech skills, receptive skills, productive skills.

Video materials in teaching English provide an opportunity to create visual language situations for the purpose of both developing language skills for the perception and production of foreign language speech and fixing lexical and grammatical material in memory by selecting situations and relying on auditory and visual representations. From a didactic point of view, audiovisual materials in teaching foreign languages optimize the mental load of students, activate cognitive activity, direct and control the process of both the formation and development of speech skills and abilities when mastering foreign language speech activity. They also develop activity and independence in doing communicative tasks, allow students to increase the time of active speaking and listening. Authentic video materials create comfortable conditions for the student to master new regional information, the speech behavior of native speakers, and help students to be acquainted with the life of the people and their culture as well. Moreover, the use of video recordings in the classroom contributes to the individualization of learning and the development of motivation for the speech activity of students. With the help of video materials, two types of motivation are developed: selfmotivation, if student feels that he/she can understand the target language in watching the video, this brings satisfaction, confidence and desire for further improvement. Another advantage of the video material is the power of impression and emotional impact on students. Therefore, the main attention should be directed to the formation of students' personal attitude to what they watch. According to some researchers who did the work in this field video materials can be classified as followings:

1. Authentic audiovisual materials - TV commercials, feature films and documentaries, TV shows, cartoons, clips, news, etc.
2. Authentic audio materials - audio books, songs, advertisements and radio broadcasts, etc.
3. Authentic visual materials - paintings, photographs, slides, road signs, illustrations, stamps, postcards, etc.
4. Authentic print materials - newspaper articles, sports columns, lyrics, programs, telephone directories, travel brochures, comics, checks, tickets, etc.
5. Realities (objects) - coins, cash, masks, toys, etc.

Authentic materials which created by native speakers, are used in the educational process without any changes, focused on a communicative approach to teaching a foreign language outside the

language environment. Today we have access to satellite and cable television programs, many of which are broadcast in a foreign language, which provide excellent opportunities for developing and improving various skills and abilities. However, many students and even teachers have no idea how to use these resources to improve their language proficiency. Therefore, the possibilities that audiovisual means have should be used purposefully. Modern technologies allow us to expand the scope of the lesson and lead to the need to use new forms of teaching. In order to use video materials effectively in ESP classes, we can use authentic videos in three stages, such as predemonstration, demonstration and post-demonstration. The pre-demonstration stage aims at removing language difficulties by introducing and consolidating new words, revising previously studied lexical units, repeating the necessary grammatical rules. The goals of this stage are as follows: to motivate students, set them up to complete the task, making them active participants in the learning process; remove possible difficulties in the perception of the text and prepare for the successful completion of the task. Here we propose to use various options for tasks aimed at anticipating the content of the video, based on: listing new words with definitions or asking the content of questions or true/false statements. The purpose of demonstration stage is to ensure the further development of the language, speech or communicative competence of students, taking into account their real opportunities for foreign language communication. Students improve logic, attention, memory and prediction of the semantic content of the text when video material is presented. The number of demonstrating videos depends on the levels of students. The demonstration should be accompanied by active learning activities of students related to managing the perception of video material in the form of annotations, abstracts, plans, key words or phrases. At this stage, teachers can use various tasks such as to search for language information, tasks for the development of receptive skills and tasks aimed at developing speaking skills. Tasks for searching language information might focus on searching, isolating, fixing, transforming certain language material at the lexical, grammatical, and phonetic levels: watch the video clip and find Uzbek equivalents for the following English words and expressions; fill in the gaps in the sentences with the necessary words and expressions; write down all the adjectives that were used in the video, etc.

Tasks for the development of receptive skills might include:

6. finding the correct answers to questions can be used (questions are offered before viewing);
7. determination of true/false statements, correlation of disparate sentences with semantic parts of the text (text plan and headings of each part are proposed);
8. lining up parts of the text in a logical sequence;
9. establishing cause-and-effect relationships, etc.

Tasks aimed at developing speaking skills might include comparing different cultures, finding common cultural patterns, interpreting various situations of a speech and non-verbal nature from the point of view of the cultural characteristics of a particular country. The final stage of using authentic videos is the post-demonstration stage, which develops productive skills in speaking or writing. At this stage, language teachers ask students to read the titles of the videos and try to guess what will be in the video lesson; write down what they already know about the topic and would like to learn. Having expressed their assumptions, the students should watch the video more carefully, because they will want to get confirmation of their guesses and will be motivated to learn new information.

Below we can state that there are many reasons for the active use of videos in ESP classes based on the principles of providing interaction:

10. video increase students' interest, stimulates imagination and creativity and develops critical thinking;
11. allows learners to overcome the barrier of misunderstanding and mistrust between people of different cultures;
12. shows the life of other people in all its manifestations;

13. provides an opportunity to compare different cultures;
14. relieves emotional stress;
15. makes it possible to use a variety of interactive forms of organizing work in the classroom;
16. allows to conduct conversations that affect a variety of moral and ethical issues;
17. provides the opportunity to hear authentic speech and imitate its patterns;
18. activates and develops the main types of speech activity (reading, writing, listening, speaking);
19. allows to see and understand paralinguistic phenomena and develop non-verbal communication skills (facial expressions, gestures, postures, distance between interlocutors, clothing, etc.);
20. presents non-verbal ways of communication directly in action.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the videos used in foreign language classes is one of the effective tools that help create an atmosphere of interest in the audience, increase the motivation of students and thereby lead to a decrease in psychological stress arising from uncertainty in on their own when students need to speak in English. Moreover, while watching videos in class, students seem to live through all the events, play certain roles, solve problems and satisfy their cognitive interests. This significantly increases the motivation and intensity of the language preparation of students for international professional communication, develops receptive and productive skills and improve the quality of teaching a foreign language in the allotted time of ESP classes.

Used literature:

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